

Focus Group Instrument

Introduction of Facilitator/Moderator

[Preamble Slides](#)

Welcome everyone! My name is Claire Miller, and I am a Lapenta intern this summer working in NOAA's Weather Program Office (WPO). I am joined by my colleague and mentor Dr. Castle Williamsberg. I will be leading today's discussion. My role is to ask questions, keep the conversation on track with our allotted time, and make sure that you all have the chance to share your knowledge and experiences. I am joining from the office, but Castle and I are the only members of the WPO office who will be listening to today's discussion. The session today will take about 90 minutes total.

Purpose of the Focus Group Session:

As I mentioned in my email invitation, today's focus group is about sharing your experiences applying to one of WPO's Fiscal Year 2025 Notices Of Funding Opportunity (which I will refer to as FY25 NOFOs). The purpose of this focus group is to build on WPO's prior efforts to improve the applicant experience during the NOFO application process. For context, this process first began with the development and deployment of the inaugural Applicant Customer Experience Satisfaction (ACES) Survey following the FY23 NOFO application deadline, and has continued annually ever since.

As a Lapenta Intern, my project this summer has a particular focus on better understanding the difference in experiences between new and returning applicants to WPO's NOFOs, which is what we will be talking about today. We hope to learn more about your experiences as new applicants to inform recommendations on how to continue improving our competitive funding process.

While we know many of you have already received a funding recommendation for your application, this focus group will not be used to discuss your individual proposals, your scores, or that recommendation. Today, we want to focus more on the journey and experience you had learning about the NOFO opportunity to which you applied, reading and interpreting NOFO materials and resources that were available, preparing your application materials, and ultimately submitting your proposal via eRA. Your participation is completely independent of your funding recommendation.

Confidentiality:

All the information we collect here today is confidential. We will use the information you provide, but we will not identify any of you in anything we do related to this focus group. For example, we will not use your name, affiliation, or any other identifying information in reports or other materials related to this focus group.

Verbal Consent:

Before we begin the discussion, I would like each of you to provide verbal consent that you are willing to participate in this focus group. This verbal consent will be our record that you agreed to participate in this focus group, you agree to being audio recorded, and you understand that we will keep information confidential. If you do not feel comfortable being audio recorded, please let us know.

As a reminder, your participation is completely voluntary. You may decline to answer any question you wish, and may choose to leave at any time during the focus group session.

This verbal consent also acknowledges that everyone in the room should respect confidentiality. If you know one another, we ask that you not talk about specific individuals or any information they share today. It is fine to talk about the general discussion, but not to identify who said what.

Are there any questions about this consent process?

We will start with [pick a person] and go around the virtual room and receive verbal consent from each person.

Thank you all for agreeing to participate!

Focus Group Ground Rules:

Finally, before we begin our discussion today, I want to go over a few ground rules.

We will be focusing on some specific topics. We are interested in what everyone has to say about them. If someone throws out an idea that you want to expand on, or if you have a different point of view, please use the raise your hand feature and I will call on you to speak. Sometimes I may have to interrupt the discussion to bring us back to the topic or to move on to another question or topic, to make sure we cover everything on our agenda.

We will follow several ground rules during this session:

1. We want everyone to express their opinions about the discussion topics. There are no right or wrong answers. We just want to understand your views.
2. Feel free to agree or disagree with what other people say. However, please be respectful to one another and give people space to share their thoughts and experiences, even if you do not agree with them.
3. Keep your responses brief so everyone has a chance to share. Be mindful of how often you're speaking compared to others.

4. Please mute your microphone when not speaking, and if you feel comfortable, have your video turned on. This helps minimize background noise and distractions, and seeing each other enhances communication and connection.
5. It's okay to talk to each other, not just the moderator. Because we don't have in-person body language, you are encouraged to use the 'Raise Your Hand' feature to speak. This will ensure there are less interruptions, and also let people build off of each other.
6. The chat feature can be used to support the discussion, not replace it. Chat can be used for quick clarifications, short comments, or sharing resources, but the main discussion should happen virtually.
7. Sometimes we will go around the table or I will call on different individuals to share their views on a topic. You can always "pass" if you prefer not to comment on that particular topic.
8. We would like to stress that we want to keep the sessions confidential. We ask you to respect each other's privacy and not repeat what you hear during the group.

Does anyone have any questions, or want to add any ground rules before we get started today?

Moderator Guide:

Opening questions

I would like to start by first understanding who each of you are as applicants. For example, being new to submitting an application to WPO does not necessarily speak to your career stage.

1. **(understanding “new”)** First, could everyone introduce themselves to the group? Please give your name, the organization with which you are affiliated, your career stage, and one thing that stands out to you about your experience applying to the FY25 NOFO as a first-time applicant

- (probe) Do you have past experience applying for research grants or was the WPO FY25 NOFO your first submission ever?

Advertising the NOFO

As WPO hosts its funding competitions every year, we often think about how we can reach and advertise to all possible applicants. The next questions will explore how you learned about the FY25 NOFO opportunity and how WPO can reach more first time applicants.

2. **(advertising NOFO)** How do you usually find out about funding opportunities? Is that how you found out about this one (the FY25 WPO NOFO to which you applied)?

3. **(advertising NOFO)** How could WPO best raise awareness among first time applicants of new funding competitions? For example, are there other advertising channels that we could have used (e.g., LinkedIn, X, community boards, etc.)?

Resources

The NOFO is a document that contains detailed instructions on preparing and submitting a funding proposal. To assist applicants in preparing and submitting a proposal, WPO provides a variety of different resources. These next questions will explore your experiences and interactions with these specific resources.

4. **(webinar marketing)** By a show of hands, how many of you were aware that WPO hosted a FY25 NOFO webinar? Did you watch the FY25 NOFO webinar? Why or why not?

- (probe) For those who watched, did you find the webinar helpful? Is there anything you can think of that would have made it more useful for you?
- (probe) For those who did not watch, would you consider watching the webinar in future years? Is there something in particular WPO could do to make the webinar more attractive or more interesting to you?
- (probe) How could WPO better advertise the NOFO webinar to increase awareness?

5. **(NOFO FAQ)** In FY25, WPO posted the NOFO Webinar Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on the WPO website. Was this a resource you referenced at any point during your application

process? If so, how helpful did you find it? (if this question creates confusion, offer to pull up the webpage)

- (probe) Do you have any suggestions on how to improve the FAQs in the future?

6. **(consolidation of resources)** Survey respondents identified a desire for a “consolidation” of the many different resource documents related to the NOFO (e.g., the general information sheet, each competition’s specific information sheet, the templates, etc.). How would you describe your experience navigating the NOFO document and the various related resource documents?

- (probe) Do you think there is a need for “consolidation”, and if so, what would that look like to you?
- (probe) What is one thing you might change to make the resources and NOFO documents easier to access?

Recommendations from the perspective of a new applicant

We are specifically interested in better understanding the experiences of first-time applicants when applying to the NOFO. The next few questions will ask you specific questions about your experiences, and ways in which we can improve our process for first-time applicants.

7. What is the single most important thing that WPO could do to improve its application process for first-time applicants? This could be something you found challenging that we should address, this could be a suggestion you have, or it could be something you liked or you thought went really well that we should continue to do.

8. Before we wrap up, is there anything else you’d like to share about your experience applying to the FY25 NOFO as a first-time applicant that we have not discussed already?

Conclusion

That concludes our questions. Thank you for your thoughtful feedback and helping us continue our efforts to improve the NOFO application process.

As a reminder, everything you shared today will be deidentified to preserve confidentiality. If you have other thoughts or feedback to share after our discussion today, you are more than welcome to send written feedback directly to us (oar.wpo.nofocompetition@noaa.gov). I look forward to using this information to help inform recommendations to improve the NOFO application process.